

ACTIVE IMMUNITY

It is obtained by stimulating the immune system to activate protective immune responses. The stimulation can be:

- **Natural:** contact with a pathogen (infection).
- **Artificial:** vaccination (administration of antigens that activate the immune system without causing disease).

Key features:

- Slow to develop
- Long-lasting (often lifelong)
- Generates immunological memory

PASSIVE IMMUNITY

It is obtained by transferring antibodies from an immune organism to one that is not immune. Passive immunity can be:

- **Natural:** maternal antibodies passed to offspring (e.g. via placenta or milk).
- **Artificial:** administration of serum or purified/synthetic antibodies.

Key features:

- Provides immediate protection
- Decline with time (no memory immune cells are formed because there is not active immunization)

